

MASTER 2nd Open Call: Execution Period Kick-Off

In April 2025, the MASTER project launched its 2nd Open Call, inviting educational institutions, content creation services engaging students in XR application testing, and SMEs or large companies (as challenge providers only) from EU Member States, associated overseas countries and territories, and third countries linked to Horizon Europe.

Applicants were asked to address specific challenges and submit proposals for evaluation. Following a rigorous assessment process conducted by both internal and external experts, 24 projects were selected for funding, having successfully met all the eligibility and quality criteria.

The execution period for these projects began in September 2025 and will continue until June 2026. During this phase, the selected projects will:

- Receive financial support of up to €100,000.
- Develop innovative educational content for integration into the MASTER platform.
- Validate cutting-edge XR technologies with students in schools and professional training environments.
- Benefit from technical, educational, and business mentoring provided by the MASTER consortium.

Throughout this period, the participating teams will design and test educational materials, ensuring their effectiveness and alignment with real learning needs, before integrating them into the MASTER platform.

The 1st Open Call focused on the creation of digital learning solutions using XR technology. Now, in this second phase, the emphasis shifts to their validation and real-world application. The selected projects will demonstrate how these XR-based solutions can enhance learning experiences, providing evidence of their impact and scalability.

Stay Updated

Progress updates on the selected projects will be shared regularly via the [MASTER project's website](#) and its [LinkedIn channel](#).

About the MASTER Project

The MASTER project (“Manufacturing Education and Training through XR”) is a Horizon Europe funded initiative dedicated to advancing robotics training in manufacturing through the use of Extended Reality technologies. By developing an open XR platform, MASTER aims to provide safe, adaptable robotic environments featuring advanced interaction mechanisms. Ultimately, the project seeks to empower non-expert programmers to create and manage XR educational content, contributing to a more skilled and technologically adept workforce.

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